

IPBES VA Chapter 6 - Transformative Governance within Policy Instruments and Initiatives

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Description: This review corresponds to the IPBES Values assessment Chapter 6. The methodology explained in this report highlights the importance of describing the kinds of capacity-building needed for the explicit acknowledgment of the different types of conceptualization of nature and its benefits and their explicit incorporation into decisions and policymaking at different levels and in different contexts. This review assesses the potential of policy instruments to facilitate transformative change.

Process overview:

Protocol:

Type of analysis/search/review: Systematic analysis for selecting initiatives

Search languages: English

Search Engine: Google Search

Sample extracted (A): 46 (A)

- **Fields extracted (A):**
 - Name of Initiative,
 - Initiative Description,
 - Website,
 - General Notes

Location and Format of the Data (A): IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(A).csv

Search terms:

TS= (TITLE-ABS-KEY (

```

(
(Environmental project)
AND
(Ecosystem service valuation initiative)
AND
(Ecosystem service valuation project)
AND
(Biodiversity project)
AND
(Biodiversity initiative)
AND
(Nature Project)
AND
(Environmental Project)
AND
(Environmental valuation initiative)
AND
(Environmental valuation capacity building)

```

Treatment applied: Each initiative was assessed against (R1). The manual used to code the initiatives can be found in (R1).

Type of analysis/search/review: Transformative Governance in Case studies Search

Search languages: English

Search Engine: SCOPUS and Web of science

Sample extracted (B): 46 (B)

- **Fields extracted (B):**

- Number
- Name of Initiative,
- Initiative Description,
- Website with mission/vision/about
- Plural Values being addressed,
- Types of Values evident
- Plural values explicitly addressed in the mission, vision, value statement of initiatives,
- ILK addressed,
- Region/Scale
- Dominant decision-making contexts,
- Pet policies,
- Hot Potatoes,
- Goals/Objectives,
- Work area boundary,
- Target stakeholders,
- Decision makers targeted,

Location and Format of the Data (B): IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(B).csv

Search terms:

```

TS= (
TITLE-ABS-KEY(
(
([name of initiative])
AND
(values)
AND
(policy)
AND

```

(transformative governance OR status quo OR institutional change OR capacity building OR integration OR adaptation)

Treatment applied: Application of defined criteria based on **(R2)** which refers to Transformative governance to **(B)**.

Sample extracted (C): 46 (C)

● **Fields extracted (C):**

- Number
- Name of Initiative,
- Initiative Description,
- Website with mission/vision/about
- Plural Values being addressed,
- Types of Values evident
- Plural values explicitly addressed in the mission, vision, value statement of initiatives,
- ILK addressed,
- Region/Scale
- Dominant decision-making contexts,
- Pet policies,
- Hot Potatoes,
- Work area boundary,
- Target stakeholders,
- Policy focus/policy elements,
- Policy relevance,
- Example of transformative governance project within initiative (reference),
- DOI/link,
- Include IPLC,
- Region of Example,
- Specific Policy Instruments,
- Category of Policy instrument,
- Elements of transformative governance presence,
- Decision making contexts,
- Resource Users (Actors), ,
- Broad Values,
- Specific Values,
- Instrumental,
- Scales,
- Leverage Points,
- In which way did the application of policy instruments facilitate (a) incorporation of diverse value approaches, b) transformative change?,
- Specific policy options identified from this case

Definition of files

ID	Name	Description of file	File Type
A	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(A).csv	Sample extracted	csv
B	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(B).csv	Database after (R1) is applied	csv
C	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(C).csv	Contains the results from the final criteria applied to the initiatives.	csv
R1	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(R1).pdf	Sample extracted + applied rules of review (R1)	pdf
R2	IPBES_VA_6.2_11-12-2020_(R2).csv	Sample extracted + applied rules of review (R1+R2) / Final document	csv